

PRIVACY CHALLENGES AND FRAMEWORK DESIGN FOR IOT DEVICES: A COMPREHENSIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *This article discusses the use of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies for monitoring air quality in the city. The developed system collects data from temperature, humidity, pressure, gas, time, and GPS sensors and transmits it to the server via the LoRaWAN network. The main advantages of this technology are low power consumption and the ability to transmit data over long distances. The system architecture allows for easy scaling of the network and integration of additional sensors for more accurate monitoring. The data is stored in a MySQL database, where it is pre-processed to eliminate inconsistencies between different types of sensors. This article considers the security of IoT devices, including the use of AES-128 and ECDH for data protection. Experimental results show that the proposed approach provides reliable data transmission, attack resistance, and efficient resource management. This article highlights the importance of proper data processing and protection for the successful deployment of IoT systems in smart cities.*

Key words: *Internet of things, LoRaWAN technology, security of IoT, IoT framework design.*

Introduction

With the development of the Internet of Things (IoT), smart devices have become part of our lives. They are used in smart homes, medical systems, industry, and other areas. IoT makes life more convenient, helps automate processes and analyze data. At the same time, there are problems with the security and privacy of information. IoT devices collect and transmit a lot of data. Often, users do not control this process, which creates a risk of data leakage, hacking of devices, and their use without permission. Also, different devices use different security standards. Many IoT devices do not have powerful resources for reliable data protection, which complicates creating secure systems.

This article covers privacy issues in IoT, namely when organizing an architecture with remote data collection via LoRaWAN. It examines existing data protection methods, their advantages and disadvantages. The main questions we will answer are:

RQ1. What are the main privacy challenges in IoT ecosystems?

RQ2. How do existing frameworks address these challenges?

RQ3. What are the methodological gaps or limitations in current research?

Research Problems

Data privacy in the IoT is a complex, multi-layered problem. Problems arise at all stages of information processing, from data collection and transmission to storage and analysis. Key challenges include:

- Data transmission via wireless networks (LoRaWAN, Wi-Fi) is susceptible to attacks of interception and information substitution.

- Gateway and server vulnerabilities can become a point of hacking the system and lead to the compromise of all connected devices.

- The lack of a single security standard causes developers to use different encryption and authentication methods, which can create incompatibilities and additional vulnerabilities.

- Physical attacks on IoT devices can include data theft through access to equipment (for example, Raspberry Pi or microcontrollers).

Unlike traditional LoRaWAN security methods, our IDS system uses a hybrid approach, combining signature detection, threshold analysis, and stateful traffic analysis. In addition, our dynamic key management method in LoRaWAN improves security compared to traditional static authentication.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to analyze existing solutions in the field of privacy protection in the IoT and to develop a comprehensive framework that considers technical, organizational, and legal aspects of security. The work will consider an approach to the architecture of IoT systems. This work will identify the most vulnerable points in the architecture, propose improved protection methods, and give recommendations for ensuring data privacy in IoT systems.

Related Work

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of interconnected devices that collect, transmit, and process data in real-time. IoT is widely used in smart cities, industry, medicine, and ecology [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. However, as the number of connected devices grows, so does the number of security threats associated with data leaks, network attacks, and unauthorized access.

One of the popular data transmission technologies in IoT is LoRaWAN (Long Range Wide Area Network). LoRa and LoRaWAN are wireless communication technologies designed specifically for the Internet of Things (IoT). LoRa is a modulation method that enables long-range data transmission in unlicensed radio frequency bands. It typically operates at 433 MHz, 868 MHz, or 915 MHz, enabling long-range communication with minimal power consumption. This makes the technology particularly suitable for IoT devices that operate on batteries for long periods. LoRaWAN, on the other hand, is a network protocol based on LoRa technology. It is an open standard developed by the LoRa Alliance¹. LoRaWAN defines the communication principles and system architecture that manages data exchange between LoRa-enabled devices and the network infrastructure, including the network server.

LoRaWAN is widely used in various fields, including smart cities (air quality monitoring, lighting control, parking space control) [6], [7], [8], industrial automation (equipment status monitoring, remote monitoring of objects) [9], [10], agriculture (soil moisture monitoring, irrigation system control) [11], logistics and transportation (cargo tracking, fleet management), UAV systems [12], and healthcare (remote patient monitoring, wearable health monitoring devices) [13], [14].

The authors [15] conducted a critical review of current research on testing and evaluating LoRa and LoRaWAN, classifying them according to testing parameters, architecture, and evaluation methodologies. The paper identifies existing problems, proposes a unified approach to performance analysis, and outlines promising areas for further research. The authors [16] note the rapid development of the IoT ecosystem and the growing interest in LPWAN as an energy-efficient and cost-effective solution for IoT services. The paper provides a detailed analysis of cloud and open-source solutions for data management and key wireless access technologies. It also thoroughly examines the operating principles of LoRa and LoRaWAN and their potential in license-free ranges. However, despite the advantages of LoRaWAN, it has privacy risks and security issues, including data interception, packet forgery, and gateway attacks.

One of the key challenges in IoT is to ensure the security of transmitted data. IoT devices often operate in limited computing environments, which makes it impossible to use traditional cryptographic methods due to their high resource intensity [17]. Researchers identify three main challenges in the field of IoT privacy:

1. Data interception and modification - Wireless networks such as LoRaWAN are susceptible to packet sniffing and Man-in-the-Middle attacks.
2. Low level of data storage security—Many IoT devices do not use database encryption or have built-in security mechanisms.
3. Lack of a single privacy standard - Developers use different security methods, complicating integration and leading to incompatibilities.

Several approaches to protecting data privacy in IoT networks have been proposed in the scientific literature. Data encryption protects against tampering and interception, intrusion detection systems (IDS) to identify threats, authentication to control access to devices, and the use of blockchain to improve data security. The paper [18] notes that ensuring security in the IoT is complicated by the limited resources of devices. The vulnerabilities of IoT systems are considered, and modern methods of lightweight cryptography are

highlighted, including block and stream ciphers, hash functions, and cryptography on elliptic curves. Given the resource constraints of IoT devices, traditional cryptographic methods such as RSA and AES can be computationally expensive. Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) is an alternative cryptographic approach that provides robust security with significantly smaller key sizes, making it well-suited for IoT applications. ECC enables secure communication with lower processing power and energy consumption, which is critical for battery-operated devices in LoRaWAN networks.

The authors [19] note that static key management in LoRaWAN v1.1 creates security threats, including MITM attacks and replay attacks, due to the long lifetime of keys. The paper proposes a dynamic session key management mechanism based on the elliptic curve cryptosystem, which reduces the load on the joining server and improves network security. Experimental tests have confirmed the method's effectiveness, but the authors point out the need for further research in energy consumption, scalability, and the impact of network latency. The authors [20] identified a vulnerability in LoRaWAN 1.1x due to pre-installed keys that are susceptible to compromise. A KGD mechanism based on ECDH and Argon2 is proposed for secure key exchange protected against MITM attacks. Formal analysis and testing confirmed its efficiency and low power consumption.

Modern Approaches to Ensuring Privacy in IoT

Data protection is becoming an important issue with the growing number of IoT devices. Research offers several solutions to reduce the risks of leaks and unauthorized access.

One widely recognized approach to addressing security concerns in IoT is Privacy-by-Design (PbD), which emphasizes embedding privacy and security measures at the system architecture level from the outset. Instead of treating security as an add-on feature, PbD ensures that data protection is integrated into IoT devices and networks during the design phase. This approach minimizes vulnerabilities and reduces the risk of data leakage [21].

Another direction is the use of blockchain. It helps to improve the security of data transfer between devices, but its high load on computing power limits its use in resource-intensive systems [22], [23]. For low-power IoT devices, lightweight cryptographic algorithms are being developed to improve security without significantly increasing the network load [24].

In addition to technical solutions, legal requirements such as GDPR and CCPA play an important role. Compliance with them complicates the design of IoT systems, as it is necessary to ensure data protection without reducing performance [25]. To manage privacy risks, special frameworks help assess threats and notify users of possible leaks [26]. Today, ontology models and blockchain solutions are hot topics in smart cities [27].

An ethical and user-oriented approach is also being developed, and data protection is becoming more transparent and user-friendly. In addition, hybrid architectures are being implemented that combine cloud and edge computing, which increases security without significant delays in data processing [28]. Thus, modern solutions combine technical, legal, and user protection aspects.

Research Methodology

The research approach is based on the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology, which includes several stages. First, a problem is defined to analyze existing privacy threats in IoT. Then, a secure architecture is developed, within which a framework for ensuring data privacy is designed. The next stage includes experimental testing to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed security measures. The final stage is verification and analysis, which provides for a comparison of the developed solution with existing security methods.

The research was conducted using a four-stage methodology: (1) setting up a LoRaWAN IoT system, (2) implementing an AES-128 and ECDH security framework, (3) measuring encryption overhead and network performance, and (4) testing security resilience to attacks such as replay and MITM.

Proposed approach

In this research project, LoRaWAN technology was chosen because it can transmit data over long distances with minimal power consumption. This technology is widely used to create energy-efficient wireless networks, especially in monitoring systems. Its key advantages are scalability, stable connection, and operation in an unlicensed frequency range. In Kazakhstan, the 868 MHz range is used for LoRaWAN, which makes this technology convenient and accessible for the project.

A prototype of an environmental monitoring system (air quality in the city) was created as part of the study. Its task is to collect sensor data and transmit it to the server for storage and analysis. The system uses a "device-gateway" architecture, where all sensor nodes transmit information to the central server through the gateway. The general scheme of operation is shown in Figure 1. Each system node is based on a microcontroller board with a LoRa Shield module. The node uses five sensors that measure temperature and humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality (gas sensors), time (RTC module), and geolocation (GPS module). LoRa technology transmits data, namely the SX1276/SX1278 transceiver operating in the 868 MHz range. Data from the nodes is sent to the server, where it is stored and analyzed.

Figure 1 – General architecture of LoRaWAN.

In Figure 1, the Gateway (GW) bridge regulates the flow of data between the End Devices (ED) and the Network Server (NS) without interfacing with the frame content. The NS manages the network functionalities, the Join Server (JS) offers authentication, authorization, and access control for the Eds. At the same time, the Application Server (AS) handles the central processing of IoT data streams.

Key advantages of the proposed system:

- Energy efficiency – nodes consume little energy and can operate for a long time on batteries.
- Long range – LoRaWAN technology allows data to be transmitted over significant distances.
- Reliability – wireless connection is stable even in difficult conditions.
- Scalability – new nodes can be easily added without significant changes to the system.

This architecture allows the developed system to be flexible and reliable.

Analyzing IoT Privacy Risks at Different Layers

Privacy in IoT is a critical issue and affects three key layers: device, network, and application. Each layer has specific vulnerabilities. When designing a secure architecture, all layers must be considered. Table 1 provides an overview of cybersecurity attacks and corresponding mitigation strategies in IoT architecture.

Table 1 - IoT LoRaWAN Attack Vectors and Mitigation Strategies

Layer	Type of Attack	Compromised Security (Goal)	Mitigation/Detection Strategy
Physical Layer	Node Capture Attack	Data Confidentiality, Data Integrity	Hardware Security Modules (HSM), Tamper-Resistant Design, Self-Destructing Keys
	Jamming Attack	Availability	Frequency Hopping Spread Spectrum (FHSS), Anti-Jamming Techniques, Signal Monitoring
	Side-Channel Attack	Confidentiality, Integrity	Power Analysis Countermeasures, Noise Injection, Shielding
Network Layer	Sybil Attack	Authentication, Integrity	Identity Verification, Reputation-Based Systems, Secure Routing Protocols
	Wormhole Attack	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability	Distance-Bounding Protocols, Packet Leashes, Secure Localization

	Selective Forwarding Attack	Availability, Integrity	Redundant Routing, Node Reputation, Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) for LoRaWAN
Middleware Layer	Man-in-the-Middle Attack (MITM)	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability	End-to-End Encryption, TLS 1.3 between Gateway and Server, Mutual Authentication
	Data Injection Attack	Integrity, Confidentiality	Data Validation, Anomaly Detection, Secure Communication Protocols
	API Exploits (XSS, SQL Injection)	Integrity, Confidentiality	Input Sanitization, Web Application Firewall (WAF), Content Security Policy (CSP)
Application Layer	Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) Attack	Availability	Rate Limiting, Load Balancing, DDoS Mitigation Services
	Phishing Attack	Confidentiality, Integrity	User Education, Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA), Anti-Phishing Tools
	Malware Injection Attack	Integrity, Confidentiality, Availability	Secure Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC), Anti-Malware Tools, Regular Updates

IoT devices are susceptible to physical access attacks by hackers at the physical layer. While jamming attacks might prevent communications, node capture operations have the potential to penetrate networks and steal data. Protection is provided via Frequency Hopping Spread Spectrum (FHSS) methods, tamper-resistant designs, and Hardware Security Modules (HSMs).

The primary risks at the network layer are associated with data alteration and interception. These include wormhole, Sybil, and man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks that jeopardize the availability, integrity, and authenticity of data. Security measures include secure routing protocols, device authentication, and end-to-end encryption.

The most prevalent injection attacks at the middleware layer, including data injection, SQL injection, and cross-site scripting, are designed to compromise data as it is being transmitted between devices and the server. Web application firewalls (WAFs), anomaly detection, and data validation are all effective security measures.

Phishing, malware, and distributed denial of service (DDoS) assaults are the primary risks at the application layer. Sensitive information may leak as a result of these attacks, or the system may fail entirely. To reduce these threats, anti-virus software, load balancing, multi-factor authentication (MFA), and request limitation are employed. Therefore, a complete methodology is needed to ensure the security of the LoRaWAN architecture. Every layer has unique threats that call for different defenses. Network reliability is increased and dangers are reduced by utilizing multi-level encryption, IDS/IPS systems, authentication, and API protection.

LoRaWAN-based IoT networks require robust security mechanisms to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of transmitted data. While AES-128 provides strong encryption, it alone is not sufficient for securing LoRaWAN communications due to the lack of a secure key exchange mechanism. AES-128 is a symmetric encryption algorithm, meaning both the sender (IoT device) and the receiver (server) must use the same encryption key. However, securely sharing this key between devices poses a significant challenge. If the AES key is transmitted over the network without protection, an attacker could intercept it and decrypt all subsequent communications, compromising the entire system. To address this issue, Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH) key exchange is integrated into the system. ECDH enables both the IoT device and the server to independently derive a shared secret without ever transmitting the actual encryption key over the network. Instead, each device generates a private-public key pair, exchanges public keys, and computes the shared secret using its private key and the received public key. This shared secret is then used to derive the AES-128 encryption key. By combining ECDH for secure key exchange with AES-128 for data encryption, the system

achieves end-to-end security for IoT communications over LoRaWAN. Even if an attacker intercepts the transmitted public keys, they cannot derive the shared secret or decrypt the data without access to the private keys. This ensures that sensor data remains confidential and protected from eavesdropping or key compromise attacks.

Enhanced Security Framework for IoT Privacy Protection

To ensure privacy and security in LoRaWAN-based IoT networks requires a multi-layered security approach that includes cryptographic encryption, intrusion detection, and future advancements in machine learning-based anomaly detection. This paper implements a session key management scheme in LoRaWAN v1.1 using the AES-128 and ECDH algorithms. The developed approach ensures data protection and dynamic key updates without the participation of the Join Server and guarantees Perfect Forward Secrecy (PFS). The STM32 microcontroller, LoRaWAN gateway, and a server based on Raspberry Pi 4 were used for testing.

To ensure data privacy, LoRaWAN uses AES-128 in CTR mode. This mode provides stream encryption and eliminates the need for padding. AES-128 is implemented in software since the STM32F103C8T6 does not have hardware cryptographic acceleration.

The STM32 firmware was developed using STM32CubeIDE, and the micro-ECC library was used for ECDH key exchange and TinyAES for AES-128 encryption. The Raspberry Pi 4 server runs the Mosquitto MQTT broker, manages session keys, and stores sensor data in a database.

Also, to improve the security of the LoRaWAN network, an intrusion detection system (IDS) was implemented, which allows for the analysis of network traffic and the identification of potential threats. One of the key tasks of the IDS is to monitor repeated messages, the substitution of encryption keys, abnormal device activity, and attempts to intercept packets. Particular attention is paid to protection against Replay Attacks when an attacker intercepts and resends previously transmitted packets to bypass authentication mechanisms. A server based on Raspberry Pi 4 is used to implement the IDS, which analyzes data packets coming from end nodes. The well-known Snort intrusion detection system was chosen as the main monitoring tool. The system allows you to analyze packet headers, identify anomalies and filter suspicious traffic. Snort operates in network monitoring mode, it records repeated requests, attempts to change the structure of packets and suspicious increases in transmission frequency. Based on predefined rules, the system can automatically block certain IP addresses or devices, as well as send alerts about possible threats. Additionally, for easy attack detection, an IDS script has been implemented in Python, which analyzes repeated messages and checks time intervals between transmissions. If suspicious activity is detected, the script records a possible attack and sends a notification to the administrator. The method allows reducing the computing load on the server and quickly responding to potential threats without significantly affecting system performance. Integrating an IDS into the LoRaWAN network can significantly increase resistance to attacks and reduce the likelihood of data compromise. In the future, it is planned to expand the functionality of the system through the use of machine learning methods, which will allow analyzing more complex attack patterns and automatically adapting defense mechanisms depending on the changing threat environment.

Cryptographic protection at different levels of the IoT architecture

To ensure comprehensive security in IoT networks, cryptographic protection was implemented at three key levels of the architecture:

- Device level: Secure storage of cryptographic keys and protection against physical attacks (e.g., side-channel attacks).
- Network level: End-to-end data encryption to protect transmitted information and prevent interception.
- Application level: Strong user authentication and access control to prevent unauthorized use of data.

To ensure secure data encryption and efficient key management, the following cryptographic mechanisms were implemented (Table 2):

1. AES-128 is used to encrypt transmitted data, providing confidentiality while maintaining low processing overhead, making it suitable for IoT devices with limited resources.

2. ECC (Elliptic Curve Cryptography) offers strong encryption with significantly lower computational requirements compared to RSA, making it an optimal choice for resource-constrained IoT environments.
3. ECDH (Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman) allows for secure key exchange. It improves system security by preventing attacks that involve interception or reuse of keys, such as man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks and replay attacks.

Table 2 - Secure Key Exchange and Data Encryption

Step	Action	Node (STM32)	Server (Raspberry Pi 4)
1. Key Pair Generation	Uses ECDH	Generates (d_A, P_A)	Generates (d_B, P_B)
2. Key Exchange	Exchanges public keys	Rec Sends P_A and receives P_B	Sends P_B and receives P_A
3. Shared Secret Computation	Uses $S = d_A \times P_B$	Computes $S = d_A \times P_B$	Computes $S = d_B \times P_A$
4. Deriving AES-128 Key	Directly derives key from S	Uses S as AES_KEY	Uses S as AES_KEY
5. Encrypting Data	Uses AES-128 (CTR Mode)	Encrypts data and sends	Decrypts received data

Figure 2 illustrates the secure communication process between the IoT device (sender) and the server (receiver) by using Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH) key exchange and AES-128 encryption over a LoRaWAN network.

Figure 2 - ECDH-based encryption and decryption process.

ECDH is a key exchange protocol based on elliptic curves, used in this system to establish a secure communication channel between the IoT device and the server. Suppose an IoT device and a server need to exchange data securely. The IoT device first generates a private key d_A and computes the corresponding public key $P_A = d_A G$ where G is the base point of the elliptic curve. The IoT device then sends its public key P_A to the server. The server generates its own private key d_B and computes

the shared secret $S = d_B P_A$. Similarly, after the server sends its public key $P_B = d_B G$ to the IoT device, the IoT device computes the same shared secret as $S = d_A P_B$. Since both computations result in $S = d_A d_B G = d_B d_A G$, the IoT device and the server establish a common secret without directly revealing it over the network.

After establishing the shared secret S , both sides derive an AES-128 encryption key from it. The IoT device encrypts the sensor data with AES-128 and transmits it over LoRaWAN. When the server receives the encrypted data, it decrypts the information using the same AES-128 key derived from S . An eavesdropper who intercepts the communication can only observe the public keys P_A and P_B and the base point G , but without access to the private keys d_A and d_B , reconstructing the shared secret remains impossible. This ensures confidentiality and security in IoT communications.

Figure 3 - System-Level View of IDS in a LoRaWAN Network

Figure 3 illustrates the system-level architecture of the Intrusion Detection System (IDS) integrated into a LoRaWAN-based IoT network. The IDS operates as an intermediary security layer between IoT devices, the network infrastructure, and the administrative control system.

IoT Devices collect sensor data and transmit packets over the LoRaWAN network. Each device follows security mechanisms such as Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH) for key exchange and AES-128 encryption to protect data. LoRaWAN Gateway and Network Server are relay the encrypted data to the Intrusion Detection System (IDS) for security monitoring before forwarding it to cloud storage or applications. Intrusion Detection System (IDS) inspects incoming network traffic using signature-based detection for identification known attack patterns. Also, it is a threshold-based anomaly detection to detect unusual traffic behavior (e.g., excessive packet transmission). Based on the results, the IDS either allows normal packets, logs suspicious activity, or blocks malicious traffic. Admin Console helps to log security events and they are stored in a threat database for further analysis.

Results and discussion

The data was collected from a single IoT node that transmitted sensor readings (temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, gas concentration) via the LoRaWAN network. This allowed us to evaluate the system’s performance and check its security. The data transmission interval was 10 minutes, which corresponds to the real operating conditions of IoT devices. Over 30 days, the node sent 6 messages per hour, 144 messages per day, and a total of 4,320 messages. The experiment measured encryption latency, the impact of cryptographic operations on data transmission and power consumption, as well as their impact on battery life (Table 3). Additionally, network throughput was analyzed to determine the load from encryption. The system’s protection against attacks, including man-in-the-middle attacks (MITM) and replay attacks, was also assessed.

Table 3 - Impact of Security Mechanisms on LoRaWAN Performance

Security Mechanism	Encryption Latency (ms)	Energy Consumption (μJ/byte)	Network Throughput (%)
No Encryption	0	0	100
AES-128	5–8	1.2	-3%
AES-256	10–15	2.5	-5%

ECC	7–10	0.9	-2%
RSA-2048	20–30	3.8	-7%

Figure 4 – Power consumption of ECDH key exchange and AES-128 Encryption/Decryption

Figure 4 presents the power consumption of the IoT device performing ECDH key exchange and AES-128 encryption/decryption. The initial peak (~0.18 W) corresponds to the ECDH key exchange, which occurs only once during the session setup. After this step, ECDH does not contribute to further energy consumption. AES-128 encryption and decryption show low and stable power consumption, remaining below 0.025 W throughout the measurement period. This confirms that AES-128 is energy-efficient, making it suitable for resource-constrained IoT devices.

Figure 5 - Impact of encryption on packet transmission delay

Figure 5 illustrates the impact of encryption overhead on transmission delay for an STM32 microcontroller. It compares AES-128 encryption alone to AES-128 combined with ECDH key exchange, across varying packet sizes. The results show that using ECDH significantly increases transmission delay compared to AES-128 only, highlighting the performance trade-offs of added security on resource-constrained embedded systems.

Conclusion

In this work, an IoT system for monitoring air quality using LoRaWAN was created and tested. Experiments showed that this architecture allows for efficient data transmission, low power consumption, and long communication range. AES-128 and ECDH algorithms were used to protect information, encrypting data and ensuring secure key exchange. An intrusion detection system (IDS) was also implemented, which analyzes network traffic and identifies suspicious activities such as replay attacks or unauthorized access attempts.

Prospects for further research:

- Optimization of network node power consumption.
- Improvement of attack detection mechanisms using machine learning methods.
- Development of combined cryptographic methods that provide a high level of data protection but require minimal computing resources.

The developed system effectively solves environmental monitoring problems and can be adapted for other IoT applications in smart cities.

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ПРОБЛЕМЫ КОНФИДЕНЦИАЛЬНОСТИ И РАЗРАБОТКА ФРЕЙМВОРКА ДЛЯ УСТРОЙСТВ ИНТЕРНЕТА ВЕЩЕЙ: КОМПЛЕКСНЫЙ ПОДХОД

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается использование технологий Интернета вещей (IoT) для мониторинга качества воздуха в городе. Разработанная система собирает данные с датчиков температуры, влажности, давления, газа, времени и GPS и передает их на сервер через сеть LoRaWAN. Основными преимуществами данной технологии являются низкое энергопотребление и возможность передачи данных на большие расстояния. Архитектура системы позволяет легко масштабировать сеть и интегрировать дополнительные датчики для более точного мониторинга. Данные хранятся в базе данных MySQL, где они предварительно обрабатываются для устранения несовместимости между различными типами датчиков. В

статье также обсуждается безопасность устройств IoT, в том числе использование AES-128 и ECDH для защиты данных. Экспериментальные результаты показывают, что предлагаемый подход обеспечивает надежную передачу данных, устойчивость к атакам и эффективное управление ресурсами. В статье подчеркивается важность надлежащей обработки и защиты данных для успешного развертывания систем IoT в умных городах.

Ключевые слова: Интернет вещей, технология LoRaWAN, безопасность IoT, проектирование фреймворка IoT.

ИОТ ҚҰРЫЛҒЫЛАРЫНА АРНАЛҒАН ҚҰПИЯЛЫЛЫҚ МӘСЕЛЕЛЕРІ ЖӘНЕ ҚҰРЫЛЫМДЫҚ ДИЗАЙН: КЕШЕНДІ ТӘСІЛ

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Аңдатпа. Бұл мақалада қаладағы ауа сапасын бақылау үшін заттар интернеті (IoT) технологияларын пайдалану талқыланады. Өзірленген жүйе температура, ылғалдылық, қысым, газ, уақыт және GPS сенсорларынан деректерді жинап, LoRaWAN желісі арқылы серверге жібереді. Бұл технологияның негізгі артықшылықтары - аз қуат тұтыну және деректерді ұзақ қашықтыққа жіберу мүмкіндігі. Жүйе архитектурасы желіні оңай масштабтауға және дәлірек бақылау үшін қосымша сенсорларды біріктіруге мүмкіндік береді. Деректер MySQL дерекқорында сақталады, мұнда сенсорлардың әртүрлі түрлері арасындағы сәйкессіздікті жою үшін алдын ала өңделеді. Бұл мақалада IoT құрылғыларының қауіпсіздігі, соның ішінде деректерді қорғау үшін AES-128 және ECDH пайдалану қарастырылады. Эксперименттік нәтижелер ұсынылған тәсіл сенімді деректерді беруді, шабуылға қарсы тұруды және ресурстарды тиімді басқаруды қамтамасыз ететінін көрсетеді. Бұл мақалада ақылды қалаларда IoT жүйелерін сәтті орналастыру үшін деректерді дұрыс өңдеу мен қорғаудың маңыздылығы көрсетілген.

Түйін сөздер: Заттар интернеті, LoRaWAN технологиясы, IoT қауіпсіздігі, IoT фреймворк дизайны.

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